

significantly among growth durations.

For maximum spikelet formation, 45 to 65 d VG duration appears to be advantageous; for HD grains, longer VG duration is not a disadvantage. All durations studied produced almost similar percentages of good grade grain. Longer VG was associated with

lower total grain numbers, resulting in lower yields. VG up to 65 d (total growth duration of 110 d) was associated with moderately high numbers of good grade grain and fairly high numbers of other grain grades.

It should be possible to combine the

character of high numbers of HD grain with any VG duration. For higher potential yields, a VG duration of 45 d (total growth duration of 91 d) is not limiting. It is possible to combine the character of HD grain with very short growth duration. □

Dormancy in some early and medium duration varieties

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The dormancy of some early and medium duration high-yielding varieties (HYVs) grown under upland, midland, and lowland conditions in Dakshina Kannada region with heavy rainfall conditions was assessed in 1984 and 1985.

The seed samples were collected 30 d after flowering and sun-dried to 13-14% moisture. Germination and dormancy (80% germination) were calculated on 25 seeds/ petri dish at

Germination and dormancy of some early and medium duration rice varieties. Brahmavar (DK), India, 1985.

Variety	Duration (d)	Germination ^a (%)						Dormancy ^b
		5 DH ^b		10 DH		20 DH		
		1984	1985	1984	1985	1984	1985	
Rasi	110	87	87	99	100	100	100	–
Jyothi	123	91	95	100	100	–	–	–
Annapoorna	106	45	75	91	97	99	100	10
KKP2	110	53	79	90	92	100	97	10
IET7303	129	70	76	85	88	97	100	10
Shakthi	135	33	56	98	84	98	96	10
Jaya	139	35	56	99	95	–	100	10
Phalguna	149	15	18	30	46	88	88	20

^aDH = days after harvest. ^b80% germination.

10-d intervals, starting 5 d after harvest, with 4 replications.

Rasi and Jyothi were nondormant (see table). Annapoorna, KKP2,

Shakthi, Jaya, and IET7303 recorded 10-d dormancy. Phalguna recorded 20d dormancy. □

Ratoon tillering in short-duration rice varieties

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A set of the 1985 International Rice Yield Nursery-Early was grown during 1985-86 dry season at Malda. The main crop was sown on 24 Nov 1985 and transplanted 16 Jan 1986. Cool temperature during Nov-Mar usually extends crop duration.

After harvest, irrigation water and 20-10-10 kg NPK/ ha were applied. Varieties with higher hill regeneration

Ratoon tillering in shortduration rice varieties. Maida, West Bengal, India, 1985-86.

Regenerated hills (%)	Entries (no.)	Ratoon tillers (no./hill)		Main crop days to 50% flowering
		Range	Average	
0-60	7	1-2	1	133-146
61-70	1	3	3	133
71-80	5	2-5	4	133-146
81-90	3	5-7	6	130-143
91-100	11	5-13	8	133-146

also showed more ratoon tillers/ hill (see table).

BW295-5, C662083, IR18348-36-3-3 (IR64), IR25621-135-1-1, IR29658-69-2-1, IR29725-45-1-1-3, IR31868-64-2-

3-3-3, IR35546-52-3-3-2, SI-P1681032, and SI-PI692033 had higher ratoon tillering ability. Flowering duration of the main crop did not affect ratoon tillering ability. □

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